

Evaluating CNN Models for Macular Disease Classification: Balancing Performance Metrics with Clinical Impact

Olubusola A. O. Adeaga¹, Dr Ibrahim Abdullahi²

^{1,2}Graduate School of Computing and Mathematics, Keele University, UK
x9b52@students.keele.ac.uk, i.abdullahi@keele.ac.uk

July 2025

Abstract

Early and accurate diagnosis of macular diseases is crucial for effective treatment. Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) provides detailed cross-sectional retinal images but relies on labour-intensive manual interpretation, prone to human error. Deep Convolutional Neural Networks (DCNN), offers a promising approach for automated classification. This study compares a standard VGG16 model with a custom Hybrid DCNN for classifying OCT images into three categories: Age-related Macular Degeneration (AMD), Diabetes-related Macular Edema (DME), and Normal. The research has two main objectives: (1) To evaluate and compare these models using key performance metrics such as Accuracy, Precision, Recall, F1-score, Mean Squared Error, and Area Under the Curve. (2) To examine the clinical significance of false positives and false negatives in the context of ophthalmic diagnosis. A pre-processed OCT dataset from Kaggle was used for model training and testing. Initial results indicated underperformance, prompting hyperparameter tuning. Enhanced versions were developed, with the optimised Hybrid_v2 model achieving the best results: 72% Accuracy, 49% Precision, 55% Recall, 52% F1-score, MSE of 0.72, and AUC of 0.85. The clinical significance of false positives and negatives in ophthalmic diagnosis were also explored in the context of the weak model performance. This study highlights how diagnostic errors can impact treatment decisions. It underscores the potential of Deep Learning (DL) models to support ophthalmologists by improving diagnostic speed and reliability, advocating further refinement and clinical integration.

1. Introduction

Macular diseases such as AMD and DME are leading causes of central vision loss worldwide (Baba et al., 2024), affecting hundreds of millions of people and posing significant public health and socioeconomic challenges. Early and accurate diagnosis is essential to prevent irreversible damage to the macula.

OCT has become the gold standard for imaging the retina, offering high-resolution cross-sectional views that enable clinicians to detect and monitor macular conditions. With the advent of DL, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have achieved remarkable performance in medical image classification, including OCT-based disease detection. However, applying CNNs to macular disease classification presents persistent challenges, such as accuracy saturation, overfitting, and vanishing gradients, which limit generalisation and reliability in clinical practice.

Beyond these technical limitations, clinically deployable models must also address practical considerations such as explainability, confidence calibration, and misclassification impact. Current approaches often prioritise accuracy over these clinically relevant factors, limiting their utility in real-world ophthalmic workflows.

This study aims to bridge this gap by developing and evaluating CNN-based architectures for macular disease classification that integrate both technical performance and clinical interpretability. By aligning DL model evaluation with clinical needs, this work contributes toward developing more transparent and reliable AI tools for ophthalmic diagnosis.

2. Related Work

DL has transformed medical imaging by enabling early disease detection, accurate diagnosis, and automated analysis of complex conditions. CNNs are particularly effective for retinal image analysis, as they capture spatial hierarchies and high-level features, making them well-suited for classifying macular diseases from OCT scans. Early Machine Learning approaches, such as Support Vector Machine with handcrafted features, achieved high reported accuracies but were often limited by overfitting and poor generalisation (Srinivasan et al., 2016). These limitations motivated the shift toward deep architectures capable of learning robust features directly from data.

Large-scale studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of CNNs in macular disease classification. Kermany

et al. (2018) used over 84,000 OCT images with an Inception-based architecture to classify Normal, DME, Drusen, and CNV, achieving performance comparable to expert ophthalmologists. Subsequent works, including Tayal et al. (2020), leveraged preprocessing frameworks and layered CNN models to achieve similarly high performance. Common architectures include VGG16/19, ResNet, Inception, and DenseNet, with hybrid and ensemble models further improving accuracy and robustness across multiple disease categories (Khan & Khan, 2024; George et al., 2023; Dio et al., 2022). Attention-based models have also been proposed to extract discriminative features more effectively, enhancing interpretability in clinical contexts (Mishra et al., 2021).

Despite these advances, most studies focus primarily on technical performance metrics such as accuracy, F1-score, or AUC, with limited consideration of clinical relevance. Challenges include insufficient handling of early versus late-stage disease, dataset limitations in demographic diversity, and a lack of evaluation of explainability, confidence calibration, and misclassification impact. These gaps underscore the need for approaches that integrate both technical and clinical considerations in model evaluation, ensuring that models are not only accurate but also clinically useful.

Dataset quality and scale are critical for robust model performance. Public OCT datasets vary widely in size, diversity, and preprocessing, affecting generalisation and reliability (Jiang et al., 2021; Tayal et al., 2020). Large, well-curated datasets enable CNNs to learn meaningful features and improve classification accuracy, whereas smaller or less diverse datasets may limit performance. In this study, we leverage a publicly available Kaggle dataset curated by Kulyabin et al. (2023), which contains over 2,000 preprocessed OCT images covering various macular disease categories. The use of this dataset ensures reproducibility and allows us to focus on developing models that incorporate clinical evaluation alongside technical metrics.

Overall, the literature indicates that while DCNN architectures have achieved impressive results in macular disease classification, there remains a clear gap in integrating clinical relevance into model evaluation. This motivates our study to assess not only the comparative performance of different DCNN models but also their alignment with clinical considerations, including explainability, calibration, and misclassification impact, to support practical deployment in ophthalmic settings.

3. Methodology

3.1. Study Design

This study evaluates the performance of VGG16 and a custom Hybrid DCNN model for classifying macular diseases from OCT images, focusing on clinically relevant metrics such as false positives, false negatives, and interpretability. The aim is to balance classification ac-

curacy with practical utility in ophthalmic settings.

3.2. Dataset

We used a publicly available OCT dataset curated by Kulyabin et al. (2023) and hosted on Kaggle (Shuvo, 2024). Three disease categories were considered: Normal (322 images), DME (147 images), and AMD (1,231 images). To mitigate class imbalance, under-sampling was applied to the majority class (AMD), following best practices (Zhang et al., 2021). All images were anonymized to comply with ethical standards.

3.3. Preprocessing

Preprocessing ensures consistency and quality, mitigating the impact of speckle noise inherent to OCT imaging (Sunija et al., 2020; Rajagopalan et al., 2021). Although, no additional preprocessing was required, as images had already been resized and denoised by the original authors.

3.4. Model Architectures

3.4.1. VGG16

VGG16 is a 16-layer DCNN, comprising 13 convolutional layers with 3×3 filters and 2×2 max-pooling layers, followed by three fully connected layers and a Softmax output. Input images were resized to 224×224 pixels. The original fully connected layers were replaced with a custom classification head consisting of a 256-neuron fully connected layer, a dropout layer (rate = 0.5), and a 3-neuron Softmax output for three-class classification.

Figure 1: VGG16 Simonyan and Zisserman 2014

3.4.2. Hybrid DCNN

The proposed hybrid DCNN combines convolutional layers with attention mechanisms to emphasize diagnostically relevant regions. It comprises three convolutional blocks with 32, 64, and 128 filters, each followed by max-pooling. Channel-wise attention is applied after pooling using global average pooling, dense layers, and element-wise multiplication to recalibrate feature maps. The network concludes with a 256-unit fully connected layer with dropout (0.5) and a 3-class Softmax output.

Figure 2: Hybrid DCNN

3.5. Training and Hyperparameters

Both models were trained using the Adam optimizer with an initial learning rate of 0.001, categorical cross-entropy loss, and a batch size of 32. Training was conducted for 20 epochs with early stopping (patience=5). Data augmentation included horizontal flipping, rotation (up to 20°), zooming, and width/height shifts. Fine-tuning of pre-trained weights was performed for VGG16 using a reduced learning rate (1×10^{-5}) to avoid overfitting. Hyperparameter selection was informed by literature and preliminary experiments.

Table 1: Comparison of VGG16v1 and VGG16v2 hyperparameters.

Feature	VGG16v1	VGG16v2
Epochs	10	20
Data Augmentation	Basic	Advanced
Model Compilation	Default	Adam (0.001)

Table 2: Comparison of Hybrid.v1 and Hybrid.v2 hyperparameters.

Feature	Hybrid.v1	Hybrid.v2
Epochs	10	20
Early Stopping	–	Patience = 5
Dropout	–	0.5
Model Architecture	2 Conv layers, 128-unit dense layer	3 Conv layers, 256-unit dense layer
Data Augmentation	Basic (rescaling only)	Advanced
Validation Shuffle	Enabled	Disabled

3.6. Evaluation Metrics

Model performance was assessed using Accuracy, Precision, Recall, F1-score, MSE, and AUC. Precision and Recall were emphasized due to class imbalance, ensuring both diseased and healthy cases were accurately identified. Confusion matrices provided granular insights into false positives and negatives, crucial for clinical interpretation.

3.7. Reproducibility

All experiments were conducted in Google Colab with version control to ensure reproducibility. Code, model architectures, and evaluation scripts were versioned, en-

abling transparent tracking of modifications and facilitating independent replication.

4. Model Performance Evaluation

This chapter presents a comprehensive evaluation of the performance of both versions of the VGG16 and Hybrid DCNN models developed for classifying OCT images as Normal, AMD, or DME.

4.1. VGG16

4.1.1. Accuracy

Both the VGG16_v1 and VGG16_v2 models leveraged the pre-trained VGG16 architecture, with custom layers added to adapt for OCT image classification. The objective was to achieve strong accuracy and reliable differentiation across the three classes. While accuracy is a widely used performance indicator (Encord 2023), low accuracy in medical contexts has serious implications, particularly given challenges such as data scarcity and class imbalance (Hellin et al., 2024) observed in the Kaggle dataset used for this study.

In VGG16_v1, the pre-trained base was frozen and augmented with a dense layer of 256 units, dropout for regularisation, and a SoftMax output layer. Minimal data augmentation (rescaling only) was applied. The model achieved a validation accuracy of 43%, indicating poor performance.

VGG16_v2 introduced enhancements inspired by successful VGG16 implementations in prior OCT research (Subramanian et al., 2022; Khan et al., 2023; Elkholy and Marzouk, 2023). These included extensive data augmentation (rotation, shifting, flipping), explicit learning rate control, and extended fine-tuning (20 epochs). However, validation accuracy declined further to 34%, suggesting that while the changes were theoretically beneficial, they were insufficient to overcome dataset-related limitations such as imbalance and small sample size.

The accuracy achieved in this study is substantially lower than that reported by similar works, which typically exceed 90% (Table 3). Possible causes include suboptimal hyperparameter tuning, insufficient pretraining adaptation, or dataset noise.

Table 3: Accuracy comparison of VGG16_v1 and VGG16_v2 with similar studies.

Researcher / Model	Accuracy (%)
Subramanian & Shanmugavadivel (2022)	97
Elkholy & Marzouk (2023)	97
Kim & Tran (2021)	96
Wang <i>et al.</i> (2019)	95
Lee <i>et al.</i> (2016)	93
VGG16_v1	43
VGG16_v2	34

4.1.2. Precision, Recall, and F1-Score

Both VGG16 versions demonstrated poor precision and recall across all classes. In VGG16_v1, precision was 44% for AMD, 25% for DME, and 45% for Normal, while in VGG16_v2, these declined further to 41%, 5%, and 35% respectively (Tables 4 and 5).

Table 4: VGG16_v1 Precision, Recall, and F1-Score results.

Class	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-Score (%)
AMD	44	46	45
DME	25	20	22
Normal	45	45	45
Macro Average	38	37	37
Weighted Average	38	37	37

Table 5: VGG16_v2 Precision, Recall, and F1-Score results.

Class	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-Score (%)
AMD	41	41	41
DME	5	5	5
Normal	35	35	35
Macro Average	27	27	27
Weighted Average	27	27	27

When compared to related research (Table 6), both VGG16 variants underperformed substantially. Studies such as Wang et al. (2019) and Subramanian and Shanmugavadivel (2022) reported precision and recall exceeding 95%. The low respective F1-scores in this study further reflect the models' inability to balance false positives and false negatives effectively, likely due to class imbalance and insufficient feature learning.

Table 6: Comparison of VGG16_v1 and VGG16_v2 with previous studies (Precision, Recall, and F1-Score).

Researcher / Model	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-Score (%)
Wang et al. (2019)	99.6	95.3	97.1
Subramanian & Shanmugavadivel (2022)	97	97	97
Lee et al. (2016)	–	83.8	–
Kim & Tran (2021)	–	98.7	–
VGG16_v1	38	37	37
VGG16_v2	27	27	27

4.1.3. Confusion Matrix, MSE, and AUC

The confusion matrices (Figures 3-4) revealed persistent misclassifications between AMD and Normal classes, with DME particularly underrepresented. MSE values were high for both models (1.75 for VGG16_v1 and 1.92 for VGG16_v2), indicating substantial prediction errors. AUC scores were similarly poor, with VGG16_v1 achieving 0.47 and VGG16_v2 reaching only 0.50, equivalent to random classification performance.

Figure 3: VGG16_v1 Confusion Matrix

Figure 4: VGG16_v2 Confusion Matrix

4.2. Hybrid DCNN

4.2.1. Accuracy

Hybrid_v1 achieved 45% validation accuracy (81% test accuracy), suggesting overfitting and limited feature extraction due to shallow architecture and minimal augmentation. Hybrid_v2 introduced an additional convolutional layer, a larger dense layer (256 units), and advanced augmentation, improving validation accuracy to 72% (Table 7).

Table 7: Accuracy comparison of Hybrid_v1 and Hybrid_v2 with similar studies.

Researcher / Model	Accuracy (%)
Khan et al. (2023)	99.1
Khan and Khan (2024)	97.5
George et al. (2023)	97
Hybrid_v2	72
Hybrid_v1	45

4.2.2. Precision, Recall, and F1-Score

Precision and recall improved in Hybrid.v2 for AMD and Normal but remained at 0% for DME, indicating poor sensitivity to minority classes (Tables 8–9).

Table 8: Hybrid.v1 Precision, Recall, and F1-Score results.

Class	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-Score (%)
AMD	52	49	50
DME	21	25	23
Normal	46	45	46
Macro Average	40	40	40
Weighted Average	40	40	40

Table 9: Hybrid.v2 Precision, Recall, and F1-Score results.

Class	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-Score (%)
AMD	67	81	73
DME	0	0	0
Normal	79	85	82
Macro Average	49	55	52
Weighted Average	49	55	52

While Hybrid.v2 demonstrated improved precision and recall for AMD and Normal, it underperformed relative to prior research (Table 10), where Hybrid models typically achieved metrics above 95%. This gap indicates persistent generalisation challenges due to dataset imbalance.

Table 10: Comparison of Hybrid.v1 and Hybrid.v2 with similar studies (Precision, Recall, and F1-Score).

Researcher / Model	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-Score (%)
Khan <i>et al.</i> (2023)	98	98	100
Khan & Khan (2024)	98	97	98
George <i>et al.</i> (2023)	96	96	97
Hybrid.v1	40	40	40
Hybrid.v2	49	55	52

4.2.3. Confusion Matrix, MSE, and AUC

The confusion matrices (Figures 5-6) show substantial misclassification in Hybrid.v1, particularly for DME. Hybrid.v2 demonstrated improved classification for AMD and Normal but continued to misclassify all DME samples. MSE decreased notably from 1.56 (Hybrid.v1) to 0.72 (Hybrid.v2), indicating better overall prediction accuracy.

Figure 5: Hybrid.v1 Confusion Matrix

Figure 6: Hybrid.v2 Confusion Matrix

AUC also improved dramatically from 0.48 to 0.85, signifying much stronger discriminative capability for AMD and Normal, though the DME class remained problematic.

In summary, while Hybrid.v2 exhibited considerable improvements in accuracy, F1-score, and AUC compared to Hybrid.v1 and the VGG16 variants, both architectures struggled to classify the minority DME class effectively. This highlights the need for more advanced balancing strategies and attention mechanisms to enhance sensitivity across all classes.

5. Clinical Impact

This chapter examines the clinical implications of the VGG16 and Hybrid DCNN model performances. By analysing their ability to differentiate between healthy and diseased OCT images, the study assesses the real-world consequences of model performance on patient care, clinical workflow, and healthcare decision-making.

Atun *et al.* (2020) emphasised “when it comes to critical decisions around human health, we cannot afford to

have algorithms making mistakes.” Thus, understanding how DL model performance translates into clinical practice is fundamental to their adoption in ophthalmology.

Baba et al. (2024) demonstrated that customised DCNN models for macular disease classification can support clinicians by enabling early detection, rapid screening, and reduced diagnostic burden. Automating the classification of OCT images enhances efficiency compared to manual identification, improving diagnostic workflows and patient outcomes.

The poor performance of the VGG16_v2 model (34% accuracy) underscores its limited clinical utility. A model with such low reliability risks misdiagnoses, delayed treatment, and worsened outcomes. In a clinical setting, such misclassifications increase the burden on ophthalmologists, who must manually verify results, negating the efficiency gains of automation. This highlights the necessity of more robust architectures or enhanced preprocessing for diagnostic reliability.

Conversely, the Hybrid_v2 model achieved 72% accuracy, outperforming Hybrid_v1 and both VGG16 variants, indicating improved ability to distinguish between AMD, DME, and Normal images. However, a 72% accuracy still implies one in four predictions could be wrong, therefore clinically unacceptable for diagnostic use. Such a model would require significant human oversight, reducing its practicality as a decision-support tool and emphasising the need for further optimisation and improved feature extraction.

5.1. False Positives (Incorrectly Diagnosing Healthy Patients)

High false positive rates can induce patient anxiety, drive unnecessary medical examinations, and increase healthcare costs. Salahuddin (2023) noted that overdiagnosis can lead to unnecessary treatments and resource strain. In systems without universal healthcare, false positives impose financial burdens from extra diagnostics and follow-ups (Moir and Barua 2022). This is particularly problematic in countries where out-of-pocket healthcare costs are high (Tambor et al., 2021; Nguyen 2019; Campbell 2023).

Bernstein et al. (2022) reported that reliance on incorrect AI outputs by radiologists increased false positive rates from 51.4% to 86%. Chan et al. (2020) highlighted radiologists may encounter over 2,000 false positives to detect one or two cancers per 1,000 screenings, raising cost-effectiveness and trust concerns. However, combining radiologist expertise with AI detections improves sensitivity and overall accuracy (Chan et al., 2024; Li and Nishikawa, 2015).

Research on breast cancer screening found that women who received false positives were less likely to return for follow-up mammograms (Higgins 2024), delaying future detection. In ophthalmology, similar trends could deter patients from attending routine OCT

screenings, ultimately worsening population-level outcomes.

For instance, the DME precision score of only 5% in VGG16_v2 implies a large proportion of patients may be misclassified. Considering DME treatments are invasive and irreversible (Nazario 2024), false positives could lead to psychological distress and unnecessary interventions. The confusion matrices for VGG16 and Hybrid DCNN models (Figures 3-6) showed frequent misclassification of Normal cases as AMD. Such errors not only waste resources but also erode patient trust in AI-assisted tools.

From a systemic perspective, false positives increase ophthalmologists' workload, offsetting AI's intended efficiency benefits. They also divert attention from true positive cases, delay genuine diagnoses, and risk discouraging screening participation. These findings reinforce the need for enhanced model calibration, ensemble learning, and threshold optimisation to mitigate misclassification.

5.2. False Negatives (Failing to Identify Patients with Macular Disease)

False negatives arguably pose greater clinical risks than false positives. Missing a disease diagnosis can lead to delayed treatment for conditions like AMD and DME, and irreversible vision loss. Perincheri (2021) showed that false negatives in AI-driven prostate cancer screening overlooked subtle abnormalities that were critical to diagnosis. Such findings underline the need for high recall in medical AI systems.

In this study, the VGG16_v2 and Hybrid_v2 models' poor recall and F1-scores indicate their unsuitability for clinical use. Misclassifying AMD or DME as Normal could delay interventions such as anti-VEGF therapy, worsening outcomes. Addressing this requires data augmentation, oversampling (e.g., SMOTE; Swastik 2025), and use of attention-based architectures to enhance sensitivity and robustness.

Encord (2023) notes that in healthcare diagnostics, high recall is prioritised over precision to avoid missed detections. Thus, improving model recall is critical to ensuring clinical safety and preserving vision in high-risk populations.

5.3. Balancing Sensitivity and Specificity in Clinical Practice

Balancing sensitivity and specificity is central to safe AI deployment. High sensitivity minimises false negatives but may lead to an increase in false positives, whereas high specificity reduces unnecessary interventions at the risk of missed diagnoses. The optimal threshold must reflect clinical context (Evans and Snead 2024). The low recall of 27% in VGG16_v2 (Table 5) is clinically unacceptable, as it increases undetected cases of disease and compromises patient safety.

Given dataset imbalance, accuracy alone is misleading; F1-score is a more informative metric. Future work should employ data augmentation, re-sampling, and cost-sensitive learning to achieve balanced performance across all classes.

5.4. Real-World Considerations and Future Directions

5.4.1. Validation and Regulatory Approval

For clinical acceptance, DL models require rigorous external validation across diverse datasets (Lee et al., 2024). Differences in devices, demographics, and imaging quality can significantly impact performance (Ong et al., 2023). Although DL systems show strong potential in disease detection, privacy concerns remain (Kaissis et al., 2021).

Regulatory agencies such as the FDA, MHRA, and EMA, mandate stringent performance, transparency, and ethical evaluations before approving AI diagnostic tools (WHO 2023). Explainability remains key as complex DCNNs are often treated as 'black boxes' (Devansh 2023), hindering clinical trust and regulatory acceptance. Interpretable AI is therefore essential for ethical deployment.

5.4.2. Integration into Clinical Workflows

DCNN tools must integrate seamlessly with existing Electronic health records (EHR) and OCT systems to serve as decision-support aids rather than replacements. Elhaddad and Hamam (2024) advocate for Decision-Support Systems (DSS) that assist clinicians without disrupting workflows, similar to Computer Aided Design (CAD) use in radiology. Integration challenges remain, ensuring interoperability, maintaining data security, and reducing workflow disruption. However, interdisciplinary collaboration can mitigate these issues.

5.4.3. Expanding Real-World Training Data

A key limitation in ophthalmic AI is the lack of diverse, representative datasets (Mares et al., 2024). Models often underperform on underrepresented ethnic or geographic populations (Tripathi et al., 2023). Future work should focus on:

1. Curating diverse datasets across ethnicities, disease stages, and imaging modalities (Impact AI 2023; Segmed n.d.).
2. Employing federated learning for privacy-preserving multi-institutional training (Fiorentino et al., 2023).
3. Conducting longitudinal studies to track disease progression and improve predictive accuracy.

5.4.4. Ethical, Legal, and Social Considerations

The EU AI Act (European Commission 2025) and related frameworks (Busch et al., 2024) aim to ensure safe, ethical use of AI in healthcare by classifying AI systems by risk. In clinical AI, accountability remains unresolved, whether liability lies with clinicians, hospitals, or developers. Transparent communication of AI decisions to clinicians and patients is critical for informed decision-making. To mitigate bias, models must be trained on diverse data and regularly audited for fairness (Boesch 2024).

Ethical AI in ophthalmology requires fairness, explainability, and accountability. Collaboration among clinicians, data scientists, and regulators is essential to ensure that diagnostic models are both technically robust and clinically safe.

While previous research demonstrated promising outcomes for the VGG16 and Hybrid DCNN architectures, both models performed suboptimally in comparison, revealing key challenges in translating DL techniques into clinically robust diagnostic tools.

The VGG16 models exhibited low accuracy and high misclassification rates, confirming prior evidence that standard CNN architectures require substantial adaptation for complex medical image classification (Chen et al., 2024). Both AMD and DME were frequently misclassified, underscoring limitations in the network's feature extraction capabilities for closely related retinal pathologies. The Hybrid DCNN models, incorporating attention mechanisms, showed moderate improvements, particularly Hybrid_v2, which achieved higher accuracy and better disease differentiation. Nonetheless, results fell short of clinical deployment standards, suggesting that even attention-enhanced architectures require further refinement for real-world use.

5.5. Clinical and Real-World Considerations

This study contributed novel insights by explicitly analysing the clinical implications of false positives and false negatives, an aspect often overlooked in ophthalmic AI literature. The findings demonstrate that while DL systems may achieve acceptable statistical performance, their clinical consequences remain profound. False negatives risk irreversible vision loss through missed diagnoses, whereas false positives increase patient anxiety, unnecessary testing, and system burden. Addressing these trade-offs requires improved calibration, enhanced interpretability, and validation across diverse clinical environments.

Given the rising prevalence of macular diseases and the centrality of OCT imaging in ophthalmology, integrating clinically viable AI systems demands not only technical optimisation but also alignment with clinical workflow, interpretability, and ethical governance.

6. Future Recommendations

6.0.1. Model Enhancement

Future research should investigate transformer-based vision models, which capture long-range dependencies and global contextual features more effectively than CNNs (Pereira and Hussain 2024). Ensemble learning approaches combining CNN, Transformer, and attention-based modules may also enhance robustness and mitigate dataset bias.

6.0.2. Dataset Expansion and Diversity

Expanding datasets across multiple institutions and demographic groups would improve generalisability and reduce bias introduced by homogeneous data sources. Techniques such as Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) and data augmentation can further address class imbalance and increase sensitivity to subtle pathological variations in OCT scans.

6.0.3. Clinical Validation and Deployment

To ensure clinical utility, future studies must move beyond retrospective datasets toward prospective trials that compare DCNN-assisted diagnosis with expert ophthalmologists in real-world conditions. Integration with EHR systems and existing OCT analysis tools should prioritise usability, transparency, and interoperability.

6.0.4. Explainability and Trustworthiness

While attention mechanisms provide interpretability, further adoption of explainable AI methods such as Grad-CAM, SHAP, and counterfactual explanations is essential for transparency and trust. These tools enable clinicians to visualise which image regions drive model predictions, assess reasoning validity, and detect potential bias. Enhanced explainability will also facilitate regulatory approval and clinician acceptance.

6.0.5. Ethical and Regulatory Considerations

Future research must align with evolving governance frameworks, including the EU AI Act (European Commission 2025) and guidance from the FDA, MHRA, and EMA. Transparency in training data, model validation, and performance reporting is critical for compliance and patient safety. Ethical AI development requires bias mitigation, fairness audits, and accountability mechanisms to ensure equitable outcomes across diverse populations.

In conclusion, while this research demonstrates the potential of Hybrid DCNN architectures in macular disease classification, the observed limitations reaffirm that

technical accuracy alone is insufficient for clinical deployment. The path forward lies in combining model innovation with explainability, ethical oversight, and real-world validation to ensure AI systems augment clinical expertise rather than replace it. With continued interdisciplinary collaboration, DL models have the potential to transform ophthalmic diagnostics into faster, fairer, and more patient-centred systems.

7. Acknowledgment

I would like to express my gratitude to my tutor, Dr Ibrahim Abdullahi, for their invaluable guidance and support in preparing this work for publication. Their insightful feedback and encouragement were instrumental in developing this article from my master's thesis.

References

- [1] Atun, V., Renna, F., Poon, C., Adcock, B., and Hansen, A. C., "On instabilities of deep learning in image reconstruction and the potential costs of AI" *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 2020.
- [2] Baba, S., Kumari, P., and Saxena, P., "Macular Disease Classification with Deep Learning," *Ophthalmic AI Journal*, 2024.
- [3] Bernstein, M. H., Atalay, M. K., Dibble, E. H., Maxwell, A., Karam, A. R., Agarwal, S., Ward, R. C., Healey, T. T., and Baird, G. L., "Can incorrect Artificial Intelligence (AI) Results Impact Radiologists, and if so, What can we do about it? A Multi Reader pilot study of Lung Cancer Detection with Chest Radiography" *European Radiology*, 2022.
- [4] Boesch, G., "Ensemble Learning: A Combined Prediction Model" <https://viso.ai/deep-learning/ensemble-learning/>, 2024.
- [5] Busch, F., Kather, J. K., Johner, C., Moser, M., Truhn, D., Adams, L. C., and Bressen, K. K., "Navigating the European Union Artificial Intelligence Act for Healthcare" *Digital Medicine*, 2024.
- [6] Campbell, D., "Record rise in people using private healthcare amid NHS frustration" <https://www.theguardian.com/society/2023/may/24/record-rise-in-people-using-private-healthcare-amid-nhs-frustration>, 2023.
- [7] Chan, H. P., Samala, R. K., Hadjiiski, L.M. and Zhou, C., "Deep Learning in Medical Image Analysis" *Adv Exp Medical Biology*, 2020.
- [8] Chen, C., Isa, N., and Liu, X., "A review of convolutional neural network-based methods for medical image classification" *Computers in Biology and Medicine*, 2024.

- [9] Devansh, "Why is Deep Learning called Black Box. Why is it a Problem?" <https://medium.com/nerd-for-tech/why-is-deep-learning-called-black-box-why-is-it-a-problem-43ac3d3ec24>, 2023.
- [10] Diao, S., Su, J., Yang, C., Zhu, W., Xiang, D., Chen, X., Peng, Q., and Shi, F, "Classification and segmentation of OCT images for age-related macular degeneration based on dual guidance networks" *Biomedical Signal Processing and Control*, 2022.
- [11] Elhaddad, M., and Hamam, S., "AI-Driven Clinical Decision Support Systems: An Ongoing Pursuit of Potential" *Cureus*, 2024.
- [12] Elkholy, M., and Marzouk, M.A , "Deep learning-based classification of eye diseases using Convolution Neural Networks" *Frontiers in Computer Science*, 2023.
- [13] Encord, "Accuracy vs Precision vs Recall in Machine Learning" <https://encord.com/blog/classification-metrics-accuracy-precision-recall>, 2023.
- [14] European Commission, "AI Act" <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/regulatory-framework-ai>, 2025.
- [15] Evans, H., Snead, D, "Understanding the errors made by artificial intelligence algorithms in histopathology in terms of patient impact" *Digital Med*, 2024.
- [16] Fiorentino, M. C., Villani, F. P., Di Cosmo, M., Frontoni, E., and Moccia, S., "A review of deep-learning algorithms for fetal ultrasound-image analysis" *Medical Image Analysis*, 2023.
- [17] George, N., Shine, L., N, A., Abraham, B., and Ramachandran, S. "A two-stage CNN model for the classification and severity analysis of retinal and choroidal diseases in OCT images" *International Journal of Intelligent Networks*, 2023.
- [18] Hellín, C. J., Olmedo, A. A., Valledor, A., Gómez, J., López-Benítez, M., and Tayebi, A, "Unraveling the Impact of Class Imbalance on Deep-Learning Models for Medical Image Classification" *Applied Sciences*, 2024.
- [19] Higgins, L., "Study reveals one reason why many women don't return for mammograms screenings" <https://www.health.com/false-positive-mammogram-results-future-screenings-8707316?>, 2024.
- [20] Impact AI, "Curating Medical Image Datasets with Jie Wu" <https://pixelscientia.com/podcast/curating-medical-image-datasets-with-jie-wu-from-segmed/>, 2023.
- [21] Jiang, L., Wu, Z., Xu, X., Zhan, Y., Jin, Z., Wang, L., and Qiu, Y, "Opportunities and challenges of artificial intelligence in the medical field: current application, emerging problems, and problem-solving strategies" *Journal of International Medical Research*, 2021.
- [22] Kaissis, G., Ziller, A., Passerat-Palmbach, J., Ryffel, T., Usynin, D., Trask, A., Lima Jr, I., Mancuso, J., Jungmann, F., Steinborn, M. M., Saleh, A., Makoski, M., Rueckert, D., and Braren, R. , "End-to-end privacy preserving deep learning on multi-institutional medical imaging" *Nature Machine Intelligence*, 2021.
- [23] Kermany, D. S., Goldbaum, M., Cai, W., Lewis, A., Xia, H., and Zhang, K, "Identifying Medical Diagnoses and Treatable Diseases by Image-Based Deep Learning" *Cell*, 2018.
- [24] Khan, A., Pin, K., Aziz, A., Woo Han, J., and Nam, Y, "Optical Coherence Tomography Image Classification Using Hybrid Deep Learning and Ant Colony Optimization" *Sensors*, 2023.
- [25] Khan, U. S., and Khan, S, "Boost diagnostic performance in retinal disease classification utilizing deep ensemble classifiers based on OCT" *Multi-media Tools and Applications*, 2024.
- [26] Kulyabin, M., Zhdanov, A., Nikiforova, A., Stepichev, A., Kuznetsova, A., Ronkin, M., Borisov, V., Bogachev, A., Korotkich, S., Constable, P.A., and Maier, A, "OCTDL: Optical Coherence Tomography Dataset for Image-Based Deep Learning Methods" *Scientific Data*, 2023.
- [27] Mares, V., Nehemy, M. B., Bogunovic, H., Frank, S., Reiter, G. S., and Schmidt-Erfurth, U., "A I-based support for optical coherence tomography in age-related macular degeneration" *International Journal of Retina and Vitreous*, 2024.
- [28] Mishra, S. S., Mandal, B., and Puhan, N. P., S, "MacularNet: Towards Fully Automated Attention Based Deep CNN for Macular Disease Classification" *SN Computer Science*, 2021.
- [29] Moir, M., and Barua, B., "More successful universal health-care countries employ some sort of cost-sharing" <https://www.fraserinstitute.org/commentary/more-successful-universal-health-care-countries-employ-some-form-cost-sharing>, 2022.
- [30] Nazario, B., "Treatments for DME" <https://www.webmd.com/diabetes/diabetic-macular-edema-treatment>, 2024.
- [31] Nguyen, J., "The True Cost of Healthcare" <https://collective.coloradotrust.org/stories/the-true-cost-of-health-care>, 2019.

- [32] Ong, WJG., Kirubakaran, P., and Karanicolas, J., "Poor Generalization by Current Deep Learning Models for Predicting Binding Affinities of Kinase Inhibitors." *bioRxiv*, 2023.
- [33] Perincheri, S., Levi, W. S., Celli, R., Gershkovich, P., Rimm, D., Morrow, J. S., Rothrock, B., Raciti, P., Klimstra, D., and Sinard, J. , "An independent assessment of an artificial intelligence system for prostate cancer detection shows strong diagnostic accuracy" *Modern Pathology*, 2021.
- [34] Pereira, G., and Hussain, M. , "A Review of Transformer-Based Models for Computer Vision Tasks: Capturing Global Context and Spatial Relationships." , 2024.
- [35] Rajagopalan, N., N. V., Josephraj, A. N., and E, S., "Diagnosis of retinal disorders from Optical Coherence Tomography images using CNN" *Plos One*, 2021.
- [36] Salahuddin, N., "What is misdiagnosis? And how bad is it really?" <https://www.patientclaimline.com/article/what-is-misdiagnosis-and-how-bad-is-it-really/>, 2023.
- [37] Segmed, "About Us" <https://www.segmed.ai/about-us>, no date.
- [38] Shuvo, S. M, "OCTDL: Retinal OCT Image Dataset" <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/shakilrana/octdl-retinal-oct-images-dataset>, 2024.
- [39] Simonyan, K., and Zisserman, A., "VERY DEEP CONVOLUTIONAL NETWORKS FOR LARGE-SCALE IMAGE RECOGNITION" *ICLR*, 2014.
- [40] Srinivasan, P.P., Kim, L.A., Mettu, P.S., Cousins, S.W., Comer, G.M., Izatt, J.A., and Farsiu, S., "Fully automated detection of diabetic macular edema and dry age-related macular degeneration from optical coherence tomography images," *Biomedical Optics Express*, 2016.
- [41] Subramanian, M., Shanmugavadivel, K., Naren, O. S., Premkumar, K., and Rankish, K., "Classification of Retinal OCT Images Using Deep Learning" *2022 International Conference on Computer Communication and Informatics*, 2022.
- [42] Sunija, A. P., Saikat, K., Gayathri, S., Varun, P. G., and Palanisamy, P., "A Lightweight CNN for Retinal Disease Classification from Optical Coherence Tomography Images" *Compute Methods Programs Biomed*, 2020.
- [43] Swastik, "SMOTE for Imbalanced Classification with Python" <https://www.analyticsvidhya.com/blog/2020/10/overcoming-class-imbalance-using-smote-techniques/>, 2025.
- [44] Tambor, M., Klich, J., and Domagała, A., "Financing Healthcare in Central and Eastern European Countries: How Far Are We from Universal Health Coverage?" *Int J Environ Res Public Health*, 2021.
- [45] Tayal, A., Gupta, J., Solanki, A., Bisht, K., and Nayyar, A., "DLCNN based approach with image processing techniques for diagnosis of retinal diseases" *Multimedia Systems*, 2020.
- [46] Tripathi, S., Gabrial. K., Dheer, S., Parajuli, A., Augustin, A. I., Elhi, A., Awan, O., and Dako, F., "Understanding Biases and Disparities in Radiology AI Datasets: A Review" *Journal of American College of Radiology*, 2023.
- [47] Wang, J., Deng, G., Li, W., Chen, Y., Gao, G., Liu, H., He, Y., and Shi, G. , "Deep learning for quality assessment of retinal OCT images" *Biomedics Optics Express*, 2019.
- [48] World Health Organisation, "Regulatory considerations on artificial intelligence for health" <https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/373421/9789240078871-eng.pdf> , 2023.
- [49] Zhang, S., Li, Z., Yan, S., He, X., and Sun, J., "Distribution alignment: A unified framework for long-tail visual recognition" *Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2021.